

Stickers for your snowboard are cool. Free [snowboard stickers](#) in the mail are even cooler. Everyone has to have stickers but no one wants to pay for them. How can you get stickers free of charge for your snowboard? This is possible with several simple and easy methods.

The simplest way is for someone to just hand you a sticker. If you're at a snowboard event such as the US Open, or the X-Games, this is unlikely to happen. These vendors are eager to give their stickers to anyone who walks by their booth.

Another option is to be lucky and buy a product. If the company is smart enough, they will often include stickers when you purchase snowboard equipment. However, this is not always possible. Some products aren't available online so they won't ship them to you so you don't get the stickers that you want. You can think of energy drinks such as Monster or Rock Star. They have some of the most beautiful stickers. I was never offered a sticker for buying a Monster energy drink from my Quickie Mart.

Another option is to ask for stickers at a Zumiez-certified retailer. They usually have a ton just sitting around taking up space so they might as well be on your board.

But there is still one problem. What can I do to get stickers free of charge?

Contacting companies directly is the easiest and most efficient way to get in touch with them. It is totally free and can even be done while you sit on your couch and watch Robot Chicken reruns too. You can either call them up, send a letter, fill out the contact form on their website or email them directly. You can pick and choose which companies to contact which requires you to hunt down email addresses and sort through all of the website mumbo-jumbo to find the snail mail info or contact form. The easiest option is to find a website or forum that has a list of this information already compiled for you. Then you just pick and choose which company to contact for your free stickers.

It isn't a perfect system, as not all companies will give you the stickers free of charge. However, many will. The companies that don't want stickers will ask you to send them a stamped, self-addressed envelope. They won't need to pay for postage and you'll receive your stickers. Some people require you to send money, usually one or two dollars. In those cases you can decide how much time and effort you really want to spend on getting your free stickers but a few free stickers in the mail with very little effort is worth it.